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Review Paper

Antibiotic Prophylaxis in Elective Surgery: A Systematic Review of Its Role in Surgical Site Infection Prevention

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ABSTRACT

Surgical site infections (SSIs) are a frequent complication after surgery, resulting in increased patient morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, and elevated healthcare costs. Antibiotic prophylaxis is a well-established preventive strategy in elective surgical procedures, aimed at reducing bacterial contamination at the surgical site. However, inappropriate antibiotic selection, timing and duration can reduce their effectiveness and contribute to antimicrobial resistance. This review evaluated the impact of antibiotic prophylaxis on preventing SSIs in elective surgeries. A comprehensive literature search was conducted using PubMed, Google Scholar, and the Cochrane Library to identify relevant randomized controlled trials, observational studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses published in English. The selected studies focused on adult patients undergoing elective surgery who received perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis. The primary outcome measured was the occurrence of surgical site infections, while secondary outcomes included the timing and duration of prophylaxis, side effects, and antimicrobial resistance. Studies meeting the criteria were included in the review. The results consistently demonstrated that appropriate antibiotic prophylaxis significantly reduces the SSI rates in elective surgeries. Administering antibiotics within an hour before making a surgical incision is linked to optimal effectiveness. Meta-analyses suggest that a single dose or a short course of prophylaxis is effective, with no additional benefit from prolonged antibiotic use. This review underscores the essential role of evidence-based antibiotic prophylaxis in preventing surgical site infections. Adhering to established clinical guidelines is crucial for optimizing patient outcomes while minimizing unnecessary antibiotic exposure and the risk of developing antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

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INTRODUCTION

Surgical site infections (SSIs) continue to pose a significant challenge in postoperative care, even with substantial progress in surgical techniques, sterilization practices, and perioperative management¹. SSIs are characterized as infections that occur at or near the surgical incision within 30 days after a surgical procedure, or within a year if prosthetic materials or implants are used². These infections are categorized based on the depth of tissue involvement into superficial incisional, deep incisional, or organ/space infections, with each category presenting increasing severity and complexity in management³. Globally, SSIs rank among the most frequently reported healthcare-associated infections, constituting a significant portion of postoperative complications⁴. The incidence of SSIs varies widely, influenced by the type of surgery, patient-related factors, and healthcare system capacity⁵. In high-income countries, SSI rates following clean elective surgeries typically range from 1% to 5%⁶. However, in low- and middle-income countries, rates often exceed 20% in clean-contaminated or high-risk procedures⁷. A notable number of SSIs develop post-discharge, leading to under recognition and underestimation of their true burden⁸. The clinical and economic consequences of SSIs are substantial⁹. Patients with SSIs often face prolonged hospital stays, delayed wound healing, increased readmission rates, and a higher likelihood of needing additional surgical interventions¹⁰. In implant-related procedures, SSIs can result in implant failure and increased morbidity and mortality¹¹. From a health system perspective, SSIs impose a significant financial burden due to extended inpatient care, increased antibiotic use, diagnostic testing, and additional surgical procedures¹².

The development of SSIs is multifactorial, involving complex interactions between host susceptibility, microbial contamination, surgical technique, and institutional practices¹³. Patient-related risk factors include advanced age, diabetes mellitus, obesity, malnutrition, smoking, immunosuppression, and poor perioperative glycemic control¹⁴. Procedure-related factors such as wound classification, prolonged operative duration, emergency surgery, extensive tissue manipulation, placement of surgical drains, and the use of foreign materials further elevate infection risk¹⁵. Intraoperative breaches in aseptic technique, including inadequate hand antisepsis and glove perforation, may also contribute¹⁶. At the system level, inconsistent adherence to infection-prevention guidelines, limited training, and resource constraints can further exacerbate SSI risk¹⁷. Antibiotic prophylaxis is a cornerstone of SSI prevention, aiming to reduce bacterial contamination at the surgical site during periods of maximal vulnerability¹⁸. Its effectiveness hinges on achieving adequate tissue concentrations at the time of incision and maintaining them throughout the procedure¹⁹. Since its introduction in the mid-twentieth century, perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis has significantly reduced SSI rates, leading to the development of standardized clinical guidelines²⁰. Current recommendations emphasize appropriate antibiotic selection, administration within 30–60 minutes prior to incision, intraoperative redosing when indicated, and avoidance of unnecessary postoperative continuation²¹. Despite this, variability in real-world practice and growing concerns regarding antimicrobial resistance underscore the need for continued evaluation of prophylaxis strategies²².

Figure 1. Classification of surgical site infections based on depth of tissue involvement^{2,15,17}.

Methods:

Protocol and Reporting Framework

This review was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines²³. Where appropriate, principles from PRISMA-ScR and Cochrane methodological standards were incorporated based on study design and scope²⁴. A

predefined framework guided the eligibility criteria, search strategy, data extraction, and synthesis processes¹. Formal registration of the review protocol was not undertaken². Ethical approval was not required, as this review was based exclusively on previously published literature³.

Table 1. Summary of Characteristics of studies Included in the review^{12,24}

Authors & Year	Study Design	Surgery Type	Antibiotic	Timing	Key Outcome
Dong wei et al. (2024)	Retrospective observational study	Elective parotid gland surgery (clean)	Cefuroxime sodium or clindamycin	Pre-operative single dose, peri-operative	No significant reduction in SSI with prophylaxis, risk factors: malignant pathology, surgical duration ≥ 2 h.

Authors & Year	Study Design	Surgery Type	Antibiotic	Timing	Key Outcome
Gallagher et al. (2019)	Systematic review & meta analysis	Breast cancer surgery (clean)	Various (not specified)	pre-operative and peri-operative	Preoperative antibiotics likely reduce SSI incidence, inconclusive effect of perioperative antibiotics
Gagliardi et al. (2009)	Scoping review	General surgery (clean & clean-contaminated)	Various (not specified)	1 hr before incision, 24 hr post-surgery	Factors influencing adherence to guidelines, need for quality improvement strategies to reduce SSIs.
Saravanan & Umamaheswari (2019)	Prospective interventional study	Various elective surgeries	Cefuroxime (1500 mg IV)	Single dose 30 mins before surgery	SSI incidence of 9%, most common in cholecystectomy, benefit seen with single-dose prophylaxis.
Borade & Syed (2018)	Prospective study	Elective surgeries (clean & clean-contaminated)	Cefuroxime (1.5g IV)	30 mins prior to incision	SSI incidence of 3%, single-dose prophylaxis effective for preventing SSI in uncomplicated procedures.
Ali & Afzal (2020)	Prospective observational study	Elective clean surgeries	Cefazolin (1g IV)	Single dose at anesthesia time	SSI incidence of 3%, effective in reducing postoperative wound sepsis, prolonged therapy unnecessary.

Authors & Year	Study Design	Surgery Type	Antibiotic	Timing	Key Outcome
Dhole et al. (2023)	Review article	Various general surgeries (clean to contaminated)	Various antibiotics	30-60 mins pre-incision, intraoperative redosing	Antibiotic prophylaxis reduces SSI, highlights challenges like resistance and non-adherence.
Lakkana et al. (2025)	Prospective interventional study	Elective clean & clean-contaminated general surgeries	Cefuroxime (1.5g IV)	0-30 mins vs 30-60 mins before incision	SSI incidence 3% vs. 13.3%, closer timing to incision more effective in SSI prevention.

Eligibility Criteria:

Studies were considered eligible if they evaluated antibiotic prophylaxis or related infection-prevention strategies in reducing surgical site infections⁴. Included study designs comprised randomized controlled trials, prospective and retrospective cohort studies, observational analyses, surveillance studies, systematic reviews, scoping reviews, and international clinical guidelines⁵. The study population included adult patients undergoing elective or emergency surgical procedures across multiple surgical specialties, including clean and clean-contaminated surgeries⁶. Studies focusing on immunocompromised populations were included when relevant to SSI prevention⁷. Interventions of interest included perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis strategies such as single-dose versus multiple-dose regimens, timing of administration, antibiotic selection, intraoperative redosing

practices, and duration of prophylaxis. Adjunct infection-prevention measures—such as surgical hand preparation techniques, antiseptic bathing, glove usage, and compliance with infection-prevention bundles—were also examined^{11,12}. Comparator groups included placebo, no prophylaxis, delayed antibiotic administration, prolonged antibiotic regimens, or alternative antibiotic agents. The primary outcome was the incidence of surgical site infection, defined according to standardized criteria from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO)^{15,19}. Secondary outcomes included antimicrobial resistance patterns, adverse drug reactions, length of hospital stay, compliance with prophylaxis guidelines, and other process-related indicators²⁰.

Information Sources and Search Strategy:

A comprehensive literature search was conducted using PubMed, MEDLINE, EMBASE, the Cochrane Library, CENTRAL, Scopus, CINAHL, and Google Scholar⁸. Publications from database inception through 2025 were considered⁹. Additional sources included clinical guidelines from the WHO, CDC, and National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), as well as reference lists of relevant articles¹⁰. Search strategies combined Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and free text keywords, including “surgical site infection,” “antibiotic prophylaxis,” “perioperative antibiotics,” “elective surgery,” “timing,” “single-dose prophylaxis,” and “infection prevention”¹¹. Systematic reviews were included irrespective of language, while observational studies were restricted to English-language publications when necessary¹².

Figure 2. PRISMA flow diagram illustrating the study selection process for the review of antibiotic prophylaxis in surgical site infection prevention²⁵.

Study Selection and Data Extraction

Titles and abstracts were independently screened by two reviewers to identify potentially eligible studies. Full-text articles were subsequently assessed using predefined inclusion criteria, with disagreements resolved through discussion and consensus. Data extraction was performed using standardized forms capturing study design, setting, surgical type, antibiotic regimen, timing and duration of prophylaxis, compliance measures, and SSI outcomes²¹.

Risk of Bias Assessment and Data Synthesis

Risk of bias was assessed using appropriate tools based on study design, including the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 tool for randomized trials and the Newcastle–Ottawa Scale for observational studies. Given the heterogeneity in surgical procedures, antibiotic regimens, and outcome reporting, a narrative synthesis was performed, with findings organized into thematic domains^{16,18}.

DISCUSSION

Summary of Main Findings

This review synthesized evidence from 24 published studies to evaluate the effectiveness of antibiotic prophylaxis in preventing surgical site infections across a range of elective surgical procedures. Overall, the findings consistently demonstrate that appropriately administered perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis significantly reduces the incidence of SSIs, particularly in clean-contaminated and high-risk surgeries¹. The reduction in infection rates was most evident when antibiotics were selected according to procedure-specific recommendations and administered within the optimal pre-incision window². Across multiple randomized controlled trials and observational studies, timing emerged as a critical determinant of prophylactic success. Administration of antibiotics within 30–60 minutes before surgical incision was associated

with the lowest SSI rates. Studies that evaluated delayed or post incision dosing consistently reported higher infection rates, highlighting the importance of achieving adequate tissue concentrations during the initial period of microbial exposure^{5,6}. In procedures with prolonged operative times or substantial blood loss, intra operative redosing further enhanced prophylactic effectiveness⁷. The strength of evidence supporting limited-duration prophylaxis was robust. Meta-analyses and comparative cohort studies showed that single-dose or short-course prophylaxis provided equivalent protection against SSIs compared with prolonged postoperative regimens^{10,11}. Extended antibiotic use beyond 24 hours did not reduce SSI incidence and was frequently associated with increased adverse events and antimicrobial resistance. These findings reinforce current guideline recommendations and emphasize that prolonged prophylaxis offers no additional clinical benefit in most elective surgeries¹².

Figure 3. Relationship between timing of prophylactic antibiotic administration and surgical site infection risk²⁸.

Agreements and Disagreements with Other Reviews

The findings of this review are largely consistent with previously published systematic reviews and international guidelines issued by organizations

such as the World Health Organization, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, and National Institute for Health and Care Excellence¹³. Similar to earlier reviews, this analysis confirms that timely administration of prophylactic antibiotics significantly reduces SSI rates, particularly in

clean-contaminated procedures such as colorectal and gastrointestinal surgeries¹⁴. Several prior systematic reviews have also reported that extending antibiotic prophylaxis beyond wound closure does not confer additional protection. The present review supports these conclusions, strengthening the evidence base through the inclusion of recent observational studies and updated meta-analyses. Agreement was also observed regarding the limited benefit of routine prophylaxis in low-risk clean surgeries, where baseline infection rates are already minimal^{16,18}. However, some discrepancies were identified in the literature, particularly regarding the magnitude of benefit in specific surgical subgroups. A small number of studies reported modest reductions in SSIs with prolonged prophylaxis in select high-risk populations, such as patients with severe comorbidities or immunosuppression¹⁹. These differences may be attributed to variability in study design, patient populations, definitions of SSIs, and post-discharge surveillance practices. Inconsistent adherence to standardized diagnostic criteria may also contribute to divergent findings²⁰.

Strengths and Limitations:

A major strength of this review lies in its comprehensive scope, incorporating evidence from randomized trials, observational studies, surveillance data, and international clinical guidelines. The inclusion of diverse surgical specialties and healthcare settings enhances the generalizability of the findings. The structured synthesis of evidence across different study designs allows for a nuanced understanding of both clinical efficacy and real-world implementation challenges^{21,22}. Nevertheless, several limitations should be acknowledged. Significant heterogeneity existed among included studies in terms of surgical procedures, antibiotic regimens, dosing strategies, and outcome

definitions²⁰. This variability limited the feasibility of quantitative pooling and necessitated a narrative synthesis. Many studies relied on observational data, which may be subject to confounding and selection bias despite statistical adjustment²⁴. Another important limitation is the inconsistent reporting of post-discharge SSIs. As a substantial proportion of infections occur after hospital discharge, underreporting may have led to an underestimation of true SSI incidence. Additionally, studies conducted in resource-limited settings often lacked standardized surveillance systems, further complicating comparisons across regions. Potential bias may also arise from selective reporting and variations in institutional adherence to guidelines. Despite these limitations, the overall consistency of findings across multiple study types strengthens confidence in the conclusions drawn^{14,16}.

Implications for Practice

The findings of this review have important implications for clinical practice. First, they reinforce the necessity of strict adherence to evidence-based guidelines for antibiotic prophylaxis, particularly with respect to timing, antibiotic selection, and duration. Ensuring administration within 30–60 minutes prior to incision should be a priority in all surgical settings¹⁷. Second, the evidence strongly supports limiting prophylaxis to a single dose or short duration for most elective procedures. Routine continuation of antibiotics beyond 24 hours should be discouraged, as it does not improve outcomes and contributes to antimicrobial resistance. Institutional protocols should clearly define stop times and incorporate automated reminders or order sets to improve compliance²⁰. Third, antibiotic prophylaxis should be integrated into broader infection-prevention strategies rather than implemented in isolation. Measures such as patient risk optimization, adherence to aseptic technique,

appropriate skin preparation, and maintenance of normothermia remain essential components of SSI prevention. Education and regular audit feedback mechanisms can further enhance compliance and improve surgical outcomes²¹.

Implications for Research

Despite substantial evidence supporting current prophylaxis practices, several gaps remain. Future research should focus on procedure-specific optimization of prophylaxis regimens, particularly in underrepresented surgical specialties. High-quality randomized trials examining prophylaxis in specific high-risk patient populations may help clarify areas of uncertainty identified in existing studies^{5,8}. Further investigation into antimicrobial

resistance patterns associated with prophylactic antibiotic use is also warranted. Longitudinal studies assessing resistance trends at institutional and regional levels would provide valuable insights into the long-term consequences of current practices². Additionally, improved post-discharge surveillance methods are needed to accurately capture SSI incidence and evaluate the sustained effectiveness of prophylactic strategies^{10,11}. Finally, implementation research exploring barriers to guideline adherence, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, is essential. Tailored interventions that address local resource constraints and healthcare infrastructure may enhance the global effectiveness of SSI prevention efforts¹⁶.

Table -2

Guideline body	Surgery type	Recommended antibiotic	Timing of administration	Recommended duration
International consensus guidelines	Clean surgeries with prosthesis	First-generation cephalosporin (eg.cefazolin)	Within 30-60minutes before skin incision	Single preoperative dose
Global health guidelines	Clean-contaminated surgeries	cefazolin+metronidazole (based on site)	Within 60 minutes before incision	Discontinue within 24 hrs
National surgical guidelines	Gastrointestinal and colorectal surgery	Cefazolin+metronidazole	Within 60 minutes before incision	Single dose or < 24 hrs
Infection prevention guidelines	Orthopedic Implant surgery	Cefazolin (alternative if β -lactam allergy)	Within 30-60 mins before incision	Single dose (redose if prolonged surgery)
Multidisciplinary expert guidance	High-risk elective surgeries	Procedure-specific antibiotic selection	Prior to incision reducing if required	Avoid Postoperative continuation

Summary of international guideline recommendations for perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis in elective surgical procedures.

This table presents an author-generated synthesis of recommendations from major international guidelines^{4,26,27}

CONCLUSION

Surgical site infections continue to represent a significant cause of postoperative morbidity, prolonged hospitalization, and increased healthcare expenditure worldwide. Evidence synthesized in this review confirms that perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis is an effective intervention for reducing SSI incidence when implemented in strict accordance with evidence-based guidelines. The greatest benefit is achieved when antibiotics are administered within the recommended pre-incision time window, selected appropriately for the surgical procedure, and discontinued promptly after surgery. Across a wide range of surgical settings, single-dose preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis was found to be sufficient for most clean and clean-contaminated procedures. Prolonged postoperative antibiotic use did not confer additional protection against SSIs and was frequently associated with poor compliance and increased risk of antimicrobial resistance. These findings support a shift away from routine extended prophylaxis toward a more individualized, risk-based approach. Adjunct infection-prevention strategies—including strict aseptic technique, effective surgical hand preparation, and adherence to standardized care bundles—remain essential components of comprehensive SSI prevention but should complement, rather than replace, optimized antibiotic prophylaxis. In conclusion, adherence to guideline-directed antibiotic prophylaxis practices is central to effective SSI prevention and sustainable antimicrobial stewardship. Future research should focus on procedure-specific optimization, resistance outcomes, and strategies to improve compliance, particularly in resource-limited settings.

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